

REPORT:

*A3.1.4: Summary of the outputs of 3.1.1
to A3.1.3*

Work package 3

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<https://mfmet.eu>

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Activity number	Activity description	Participants (Lead in bold)
A3.1.4 M6	UofG supported by INESC MN, RISE, IPQ, and LEI will provide a report summarising the outputs of A3.1.1 to A3.1.3 including the design and the development of feasibility studies and appropriate methodology for A3.2.1 to A3.2.4 and A3.4.1 to A3.4.3.	UofG , INESC MN, RISE, IPQ, LEI

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1. Scope

This document summarises the outputs from Tasks A3.1.1 to A3.1.3, with a focus on suitable designs and methodologies for establishing feasibility studies in leakage detection, burst pressure measurements and bonding strength testing.

2. Definitions

As detailed in Report A3.1.2, burst pressure testing and leakage testing are different: the former is destructive while the latter is non-destructive. Both can be based on either hydraulic or pneumatic approaches. The definitions of key parameters are:

- **Leakage Rate:** The volumetric or mass flow rate of fluid passing through a defect or seal under pressure, typically expressed in units of Pa·m³/s or mbar·l/s.
- **Burst Pressure:** The pressure at which a component catastrophically fails or ruptures. This is usually significantly higher than the normal operating pressure.
- **Hydraulic Testing:** A pressure test using a liquid, typically water or oil, to verify structural integrity or leak-tightness.
- **Pneumatic Testing:** A pressure test using a compressible gas, often helium, air or nitrogen, which poses a higher risk due to the energy stored in compressed gas.
- **Bonding strength:** The maximum stress or pressure that the bonded interface between device layers can withstand before delamination or leakage occurs.

3. Considerations for feasibility studies

The design of testing must align with device materials, channel geometry, intended use, safety considerations, and environmental factors.

Firstly, the gas permeability of materials used for microfluidic devices should be considered when choosing pneumatic methods. The suitability of the device for operation under high pressure or vacuum should be examined. The same principles apply to connectors and tubing. Detailed material properties are included in Report A3.1.1.

Secondly, the selected testing method should be compatible with the intended use. In this regard, considerations of the required precision, the operating pressure and temperature ranges, the intended operating medium, and practical issues (such as liquid or gas handling and safety) should all be examined. Report A.3.1.2 provides a detailed comparison between gas-based and liquid-based approaches for leakage and burst pressure testing.

Thirdly, the selection of sensors and detection methods should also align with the intended use. There is a range of commercially available flow sensors, pressure sensors, and temperature sensors. It is important that the sensitivity and operating ranges of the selected sensors meet the requirements for the test. Furthermore, real-time monitoring of flow and pressure data, with temperature compensation, is essential to achieve metrological robustness. Report A.3.1.3 lists a range of commonly used sensors for microfluidic applications.

Special attention should be paid to the connection interfaces between devices and tubing, which are often the weak points in the system.

4. Conclusions

Currently, hydraulic methods remain the gold standard for high-accuracy leakage and burst pressure assessments due to the use of the incompressible liquid media. These tests are compatible with the majority of microfluidic applications and therefore can be easily implemented as routine monitoring procedures.

Pneumatic methods using gas offer rapid and highly sensitive detection of small leakages. However, safety risks are significant concerns. A failure can be explosive, and testing must be conducted within reinforced enclosures.

Rule of thumb:

- Leak Detection: Prefer liquid-compatible tests unless ultra-sensitive detection is required.
- Burst Testing: Use hydraulic methods where possible for safety and fidelity to actual conditions.
- Bonding testing: Delamination under combined thermo–mechanical load is the primary failure mode.